

Fish Welfare – A Case Study: Reviling for the first-time side effects of vaccination in European sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) and barramundi (*Lates calcarifer*) in the Israeli fish farming

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Keywords: barramundi, fish-processing, granulomas, sea bass, side effects, vaccination, vaccine adjuvant, welfare

Vaccination is an effective way to control many infectious diseases in fish. Israeli fish farming has successfully used two vaccines over the last 30 years and has no problem with the side effects of vaccination. However, after introducing new species, a new problem emerged: these fish, after vaccination, demonstrated peritoneal lesions such as

granulomas. At the same time, the fish did not show retarded growth or suffering during the fattening period. This study was conducted to establish the connection between vaccination and the appearance of granulomas. Evidence drawn from this research work

and comparing vaccinated and non-vaccinated fish confirms that intraperitoneal granulomas do not impact the growth, performance, or fish fillet quality at harvest.